

Prognostic Regulation of Socio-Psychological Adaptation at Deviant Behavior in the Logic of the Systems Theory

Anna I. Akhmetzyanova**

^aKazan Federal University, 420008, Kazan (Russia), 18 Kremlyovskaya street

Abstract

This article justifies the selection of the systems method as a methodological basis for the study of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation at deviant behavior. The systemacity of the study of the phenomenon of socio-psychological adaptation might be fully explicated through the development of a holistic socio-psychological concept of socio-psychological adaptation as a system of restructuring of a person's behavior in accordance with the changes in external requirements. This system is based on paradigmatic provisions of the systems method. The implementation of methodological provisions of this approach allows us to deeply and constructively reveal the phenomenon of socio-psychological adaptation as a system. Using this approach as a methodological basis, we can study the phenomenon of socio-psychological adaptation at its main characteristics.

Keywords: prognostic regulation, socio-psychological adaptation, systems method.

© 2019 Anna I. Akhmetzyanova

This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

Published by Kazan federal university and peer-reviewed under responsibility of IFTE-2019 (V International Forum on Teacher Education)

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +79872904623; e-mail address: Anna.Ahmetzyanova@kpfu.ru

Introduction

Recently, the researchers have been paying more and more attention to studying the possibilities and prospects of the systems method in the modern world (Barabanschikov, 2003; OreI, 2005; Mazilov, 2007; Karpov, 2004, 2011; Povarenkov, 2017). As noted by Barabanschikov (2003), the main problem with implementation of the systems method in psychological science at the current stage is associated with the need to “study this or that phenomenon without losing its systemic (integral) qualities, the connections with other phenomena of subjects’ life and activity, the holistic nature of their development in time, and a multi-level nature of their organization. This condition implies the development of conceptual techniques that allow integrating the empirical data, research methods and concepts which belong to different scientific paradigms. Their appearance opens up new opportunities for moving in new directions in the theoretical space” (Barabanschikov, 2003). The systems-genetic approach developed by Shadrikov (1982) also remains quite promising today. Speaking about the possibilities of the systems method in the modern world, Karpov (2004, 2011) writes about the essential and radical need for its improvement: the systems method “must reach the new level of its development”.

At the current stage of its development, the systems method has three varieties – integrated, structural, and holistic (Karpov, 2004, 2011).

Today, the development of the systems method moves in three directions: systemology as a theory of technical means, system engineering as a practice-oriented direction, and systems analysis as a general scientific methodology. At the same time, if we consider other studies concerning methodological principles of the systems method, we will see that some new specific modifications of the systems method have been developed as well.

Purpose and objectives of the study

Implementation of the systems method as a methodological basis implies systematic study of the phenomenon of socio-psychological adaptation which will ensure the integration of structural, procedural and result-oriented features of socio-psychological adaptation in terms of micro-systemic (the inner content of socio-psychological adaptation) and macro-systemic (in the context of the socialization process – as the socialization effect) characteristics.

The purpose of the study is to determine methodological approaches to studying prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation at deviant behavior.

Literature review

Describing the meta-systems method, Karpov (2004, 2011) writes that, according to the so-called “classic” systems method, any system acts as a part of more specific, more general integrity – as a meta-system – which has an external localization. Being a part of a meta-system and actively interacting with it, the system itself acquires its ontological status. At the same time, the external localization of a meta-system in relation to the system is not the only possible option. Researchers have proved the existence of systems which may contain more general meta-system in their own structure. The “internally localized” meta-system determines the emergence of a specific meta-systems level of organization of the system itself (Karpov, 2004, 2011).

According to the provisions of the meta-systems method, the systemic organization of the world should reflect the systemic nature of the organization of the object. This requires the integrity of the systemic construction of any studied phenomenon, which includes five levels of analysis:

1) the meta-systems level of the analysis which implies the study of a meta-system in relation to the studied object in the criteria-based content of its qualitative determinacy and specificity which it acquires in the meta-system; 2) the study of the structural organization of an object including components and relationships; 3) the study of the functional content of the studied object; 4) the study of the genesis of the object studied; 5) integration of the previously mentioned aspects of the analysis into a single holistic picture (Karpov, 2011).

The systems-diachronic approach developed by Shamionov (2013) is aimed at studying the temporal sequence of manifestations of the studied psychological phenomenon, its changes and development in terms of qualitative and quantitative characteristics (Arendchuk, 2013). In socio-psychological aspect, the diachronic principle involves monitoring the procedure of the occurrence of the studied phenomenon on the one hand, and searching for changes in institutional formations (both progressive and regressive) on the other. It also monitors the consistency / inconsistency of their formation (Shamionov, 2013).

In general scientific understanding, diachrony describes the changes of some phenomenon or its constituent elements in time (Shamionov, 2013). According to Kryukov (2008), diachrony reveals the sequence of events or phenomena, the rate of their evolution, the pace and rhythm of the development of certain processes. At the same time, all changes have a multi-vector nature: they are being implemented both in the direction of progress and in the direction of regress and affect the qualitative and quantitative characteristics.

Methodology

In accordance with the provisions of the systems method, socio-psychological adaptation is defined as a multi-level multi-component non-linear system that characterizes the process of active restructuring of the behavior according to the changes in the requirements of the external environment.

Regardless of the variety of the systems method, the main core of its research system algorithm consists of the following six principles (Lomov, 1984, 1989, 1996):

1) Mental phenomena should be analyzed from various points of view: as a certain qualitative unit, as an internal condition of interrelation and interaction of the studied object and the environment, as a set of qualities acquired by an individual, and as a result of the activity of the micro-systems of human body (integral description of a phenomenon implies combination of all research aspects).

2) Mental phenomena should be studied from different angles and in different measurement systems due to their multidimensionality.

3) The system of mental phenomena has a multi-level nature; the psyche as a whole may be divided into cognitive, communicative, and regulatory parts – each divided into certain sub-levels.

4) Systemic study of an object requires consideration of a set of various properties since human properties are organized into an integrated unity with the structure that resembles a pyramid: the main mental properties are at the top, the properties that reveal them are at the bottom, and the edges are represented by various categories of mental properties.

5) The analysis of the plurality of determinants of the studied mental phenomenon (causal relationships, general and special prerequisites of mental phenomena, mediating links, various external and internal factors). At the same time, in some conditions the same determinants may play the role of prerequisites, while in other conditions they may act as an independent factor or a mediating link.

6) The need to study mental phenomena in their dynamics since mental development of a person is a permanent movement, emergence, formation and transformation of one's basic qualities and properties (Lomov, 1984, 1989, 1996).

Results

The main properties of the studied objects within the systems method are integrity, hierarchy, structuring, plurality and systemacity. The features of the implementation of these properties in the study of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation at normative and deviant behavior are presented in table 1.

Table 1. *Manifestations of systemic properties in the study of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation*

Properties (characteristics) of a system	Manifestations of systemic properties in the study of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation
Integrity	The consistency of structural organization of prognostic regulation (which includes three levels of forecasting: anticipatory, prognostic, and motivational levels), socio-psychological adaptation (including structural and substantive parameters of adaptability, self-acceptance, acceptance of others, emotional comfort, internality and quest for domination).
Hierarchy	The levels of forecasting (anticipatory, prognostic, and motivational levels) in the system of predictive regulation of socio-psychological adaptation are arranged hierarchically according to the level of arbitrariness and awareness of regulatory processes.
Structuration	Structuration of the system of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation reveals itself in specificity of interrelations of regulatory-prognostic processes and structural and substantive parameters of socio-psychological adaptation at normal (at different ages) and deviant (addictive and delinquent) behavior.
Plurality	The number of regulatory and prognostic processes in all three levels of the system of prognostic regulation varies in different methodological approaches; models describing structural components also vary depending on scientific school which different authors belong to.
Systemacity	The properties and specifics of the functioning of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation are determined by the properties of the three levels of forecasting and by the properties that are determined by the system of interrelations of regulatory-prognostic processes and structural-substantial parameters of social-psychological adaptation.

The analysis of prognostic mechanisms of socio-psychological adaptation at deviant behavior should be carried out with consideration of the diachronicity principle which helps to understand not only the nature of temporary changes (the specifics of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological regulation at different age stages – adolescence, adolescence, adulthood – as well as the features of prognostic regulation at deviant – addictive and delinquent – behavior), but also the specifics of the formation of prognostic regulation levels (prognostic, anticipatory, motivational), that is, those intra-level and inter-level

changes that create the basis for the progress (changes) of the whole system (Table 2).

Table 2. *The implementation of the systems method in the analysis of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation at deviant behavior*

Systems analysis levels	Prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation (theoretical foundation)	Prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation (empirical foundation)
<p>1) structural (systems which has their own specific patterns)</p>	<p>Interpersonal interaction which is considered as a determinant for the phenomenon of a socio-psychological adaptation embeds and determines the structural and substantive composition of socio-psychological adaptation through prognostic regulation which is implemented at three levels (anticipatory, prognostic, motivational).</p> <p>The socio-psychological adaptation, which represents the system of restructuring of behavior in accordance with the changes in external requirements, is studied not only in terms of its own (internal) and external (social) content, but also in terms of new personal formations, multi-level intra-and inter-functional characteristics and their interconnections emerging in the process of adaptation.</p>	<p>The system of prognostic regulation includes three levels of prediction – anticipatory, prognostic and motivational; It is organized based on a structural principle and forms unity which includes three levels of forecasting as well as their interrelations. In normal state, the prognostic structure of regulation of socio-psychological adaptation represents an integrated system characterized by high adaptability which is determined by high rates of self-acceptance, acceptance of others, emotional comfort, and internality at a low tendency to dominance, as well as by a high anticipatory and prognostic consistency.</p>
<p>2) functional (functioning of a system within its macro-structure)</p>	<p>Socio-psychological adaptation functions within the “norm-deviation” continuum and is being implemented through prognostic regulation in interpersonal interaction.</p> <p>The development of behavioral deviations leads to a qualitative transformation of the prognostic structure of regulation of socio-psychological adaptation.</p>	<p>Being a dynamic system, socio-psychological adaptation has a variable structural organization which maintains overall integrity during the development of behavioral deviations. The causes of destructive changes are determined at the level of interconnectedness of structural and substantive parameters of socio-psychological adaptation, as well as at the levels of forecasting and regulatory processes that determine structural organization of the socio-psychological adaptation phenomenon.</p>

3) genetic (the dynamics of the formation and implementation of the systemic qualities of the object studied)	Being a dynamic system, socio-psychological adaptation has a variable structural organization which maintains overall integrity during the development of behavioral deviations.	The genetic aspect of the analysis of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation reveals itself through the study of transformation of prognostic structure of regulation of socio-psychological adaptation at different age stages (in childhood, adolescence, adulthood), which made it possible to identify common patterns of genesis and systemogenesis constituting the dialectical unity
4) integrative (implementation of systemic qualities in external interactions)	The evaluation of prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation within the norm-pathology range at the social level allows predicting deviant manifestations both on level of society as a whole and on the level of separate social groups.	Prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation, both at a normal behavior (at different age stages) and at behavioral deviations is characterized by a three-factor structure that includes anticipatory-perspective, internally-analytical and regulatory-adaptive factors, which may be implemented through interpersonal interaction strategies in the time-spatial continuum.

Thus, the implementation of the systems method in studying the predictive regulation of socio-psychological adaptation at deviant behavior helps to reveal not only structural and substantive characteristics (the result-based aspect of the study), but also the features of functioning and the genesis of prognostic mechanisms of socio-psychological adaptation (procedural-dynamic aspect of the study).

The system of prognostic regulation includes three levels of forecasting – anticipatory, prognostic and motivational – which regulate socio-psychological adaptation. The level of anticipation reveals unconscious regulation, which is being implemented through anticipatory consistency. The system of conscious self-regulation of behavior which reveals the content of the prognostic level represents a multi-level process of a person's mental activity in setting goals and managing their achievement. It includes operational and self-regulatory levels (Morosanova, 2010). The processes of conscious self-regulation of behavior determine the arbitrary level of regulation of forecasting processes. The motivational level of the system of prognostic regulation is implemented through social and psychological attitudes in motivational sphere and it characterizes the motivational orientation of a subject.

Discussions

Considering socio-psychological adaptation as a system for restructuring of behavior in accordance with the changes in external requirements, it can be most fully and constructively presented in the logic of the systems method which allows considering socio-psychological adaptation not only in terms of its own (internal) and external (social) content, but also in terms of new personal formations, multi-level intra/inter-functional characteristics, their interrelations, and multidirectional dynamics.

Conclusion

Thus, the implementation of the systems method in studying the prognostic regulation of socio-psychological adaptation at deviant behavior helps to reveal not only structural and substantive characteristics (the result-based aspect of the study), but also the features of functioning and the genesis of prognostic mechanisms of socio-psychological adaptation.

Acknowledgment

The work is performed according to the Russian Government Program of Competitive Growth of Kazan Federal University.

The study was carried out with the support of the Russian Foundation for Basic Research in the framework of the research project No. 18-013-01012 “Subjective experience of mental states in life prediction situation”.

References

- Arendchuk, I. V. (2013). Adaptive Readiness of an Individual for Educational and Professional Activities: a System-Diachronic Approach. *Modern studies of social issues (electronic scientific journal)*, 10(30), 27.
- Barabanschikov, V. A. (2003). System Organization and Mentality Development. *Psychological Journal*, 1, 29-46.
- Karpov, A. V. (2004). *Metasystem Organization of Mental Tier Structures*. Moscow: Institute of Psychology, Russian Academy of Sciences.
- Karpov, A. V. (2011). *Psychology of Consciousness. Meta-Systems method*. Moscow: Russian Academy of Sciences publishing house.
- Kryukov, V. V. (2008). *Matter and Being in the Diachronic Version*. Novosibirsk: NSTU publishing house.
- Lomov, B. F. (1984). *Methodological and Theoretical Issues of Psychology*. Moscow: Nauka.
- Lomov, B. F. (1989). The Systems Method and the Issue of Determinism in Psychology. *Voprosy Psichologii*, 10(4), 19-34.
- Lomov, B. F. (1996). *Systemicity in psychology*. Moscow: Voronezh: APSN.
- Morosanova, V. I. (2010). *Self-Regulation and Individuality of a Person*. Moscow: Nauka.
- Mazilov, V. A. (2007). Methodology of Psychological Science: issues and Prospects. *Psychology. Higher School of Economics journal*, 4(2), 3-21.
- Orel, V. E. (2005). Features of Manifestation of Psychological Burnout in the Motivational Sphere of Personality. *The Messenger Tomsk State Pedagogical University*, 1(45), 55-62.
- Povarenkov, Y. P. (2017). Structural-Level Approach to Periodization of the Personality's Professional Formation. *Yaroslavl Pedagogical Journal*, 6(2), 212-219.
- Shamionov, R. M. (2013). Socialization of Personality: Systematic-Diachronic Approach. *Psikhologicheskie Issledovaniya*, 6(27), 8. URL: <http://psystudy.ru> (request date: 12/30/2018).
- Shadrikov, V. D. (1982). *Issues of professional activity systemogenesis*. Moscow: Nauka.